

////////////////////////////////////

PREDICTING DESIGN STUDENT SUCCESS ACROSS THE DESIGN DISCIPLINES

A LOOK AT ARCHITECTURE, GRAPHIC DESIGN, INTERIOR DESIGN, AND LANDSCAPE ARCHITECTURE

Lori Brunner-Stone, Paul R. Bruski
Iowa State University
lbrun@iastate.edu, bruski@iastate.edu

ABSTRACT

The main focus of this paper is to answer the question, 'what measures are the best in predicting a student's success in college.' In particular, this paper addresses a student who is interested in one of the design disciplines (architecture, graphic design, interior design, or landscape architecture) within a College of Design at a university in the United States. Data from four predictor domains in college admissions (Camara, 2005), were collected and analyzed, including: 1) cognitive measures (ACT, High School GPA and Rank), 2) non-cognitive scales that include personality and motivation scales (the Big Five Personality Test, and Raven's Advanced Progressive Matrices), 3) personal qualities found in portfolios and essays, and 4) other factors, such as high school characteristics (location of high school) and legacy/alumni parental relation to applicant. The success measure, or criterion variable, used in this study was a student's cumulative GPA.

Keywords: selection criteria, multi,-disciplinary design, predicting academic success.

CONTEXT / PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

The main focus of this paper is to answer the question, 'what measures are the best in predicting a student's success in college.' In particular, this paper addresses a student who is interested in one of the design disciplines (architecture, graphic design, interior design, or landscape architecture) within a College of Design at a university in the United States. This question is important for a number of reasons. The rising cost of tuition, coupled with enrollment management in all of the design programs of this college create a healthy competitive environment

where students, parents, and educators are demanding an admissions process that is transparent, equitable, and fair; where the admissions criteria correspond to a program's mission; and where a student is assessed as holistically as possible, instead of a set of measures that may only identify a narrow range of skills, aptitudes, and abilities. It is hypothesized that the current selection criteria used in these design programs are not consistent with the best measures that predict a student's later academic success. More broadly, design programs in general may be using selection criteria that are out of date or not well suited to design student assessment.

There are many prediction studies of academic admissions in fields outside of design such as psychology, business, law, and medicine (Camara, 2005). In contrast, design has had minimal attention in this area. In a time where design and creativity are at the forefront of our society and culture, there has not been a comprehensive investigation into how one identifies a student who shows potential in one of the many disciplines of design.

The intention of this study is to uncover the nuances and subtle differences, in addition to the similarities of these design students so we can better understand and respond to admission and selection responsibilities in the various design programs.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Predictors demonstrate their importance and relevance through their ability to envisage the criteria of interest to colleges and universities. Camara (2005) argues for broadening the criteria and

model for college success, and discusses five predictor domains in college admissions including: 1) Cognitive Measures such as standardized tests (SAT I, ACT, GRE), high school rank and GPA, 2) Non-cognitive Scales such as personality tests, self-reports, and qualities of a student such as motivation, intellectual curiosity, and interests, 3) Personal Qualities that would be found in letters of recommendation, portfolios, essays, interviews, and biographical and experience shown in special projects or research, extracurricular activities and leadership activities, 4) Applicant Characteristics such as race/ethnicity, gender, ability to pay, and veteran/military service, and 5) Other, such as high school characteristics (number of AP courses, location of high school), contextual factors such as institutional priorities, competitiveness of applicant pool, and legacy/alumni recommendation.

Currently the most popular approach among psychologists for studying personality traits is the five-factor model or the Big Five dimensions of personality. The five dimensions include: neuroticism, extroversion, openness, agreeableness, and conscientiousness. Research suggests that the Big Five traits, collectively, outperformed academic motivation, IQ, high school GPA, SAT scores, and ability, to predict academic success (Conrad, 2006; Nofhle & Robins, 2007; Duckworth & Seligman, 2005). Persons scoring high in openness have completed more years of academic training by middle adulthood (Goldberg, Sweeney, Merenda, & Hughes, 1998). Openness also predicts success in artistic jobs, while conscientiousness predicts success in conventional jobs (Barrick, Mount, & Gupta, 2003; Larson, Rottinghaus, & Borgen, 2002). This is using Holland's RIASEC typology of vocations, which include six types—realistic, investigative, artistic, social, enterprising, and conventional. In college, conscientiousness also predicts higher academic grade-point averages GPAs in school (Komarraju, Karau, & Schmeck, 2009; Nofhle & Robins, 2007; Paunonen, 2003). This personality trait has consistently positive association with GPA beyond that explained by SAT scores (Conard, 2006), high school GPA (Nofhle & Robins, 2007), IQ (Duckworth & Seligman, 2005), or motivation (Komarraju, Karau, & Schmeck, 2009). Conscientiousness, beyond primary

and secondary schooling, has emerged as a general predictor of job performance across a wide range of jobs (Barrick & Mount, 1991; Mount, Barrick, & Stewart, 1998). Neuroticism is an important predictor of job satisfaction. Persons scoring high in neuroticism are more likely to experience burnout and to change jobs, whereas more stable individuals feel satisfied and committed to their organizations (Thoresen, Kaplan, Barsky, Warren, & de Chermont, 2003). Admissions decisions, however, are rarely based on personality trait scores. The predominant form of admissions criteria include initial GPA, standardized tests, and portfolio reviews in the case of interior design programs.

METHODOLOGY

This paper addresses results from completed research. In this project, the researchers looked at a comprehensive list of student information and admissions variables for undergraduate students enrolled in four of the design programs within the College of Design: architecture, graphic design, interior design, and landscape architecture. The criterion variable, a student's academic success, is defined by their university cumulative grade point average.

PARTICIPANTS

All undergraduate students that were enrolled in one of the four design disciplines in the college of design were invited to participate. This included a total of 797 students with 272 from architecture, 235 from graphic design, 147 from interior design, and 143 from landscape architecture.

DATA INSTRUMENTS

Data from four predictor domains in college admissions (Camara, 2005), were collected and analyzed, including: 1) cognitive measures (ACT, High School GPA and Rank), 2) non-cognitive scales that include personality and motivation scales (the Big Five Personality Test, and Raven's Advanced Progressive Matrices), 3) personal qualities found in portfolios and essays, and 4) other factors, such as high school characteristics (location of high school) and legacy/alumni parental relation to applicant.

More specifically, the cognitive measures collected included the ACT composite and subscores¹, high school GPA and high school rank. The noncognitive predictor scale used was the Big Five Personality Test, which include the five personality factors of: 1) Neuroticism—level of stability versus instability, 2) Extraversion—tendency to be assertive, sociable, and energetic 3) Openness—disposition to be curious, open to new situations, and imaginative, 4) Agreeableness—disposition to be cooperative, and supportive, and 5) Conscientiousness—disposition toward purposeful, determined, and goal-directed behavior (Barrick, Mount, & Gupta, 2003; Larson, Rottinghaus, & Borgen, 2002; Loehlin, McCrae, Costa, & John, 1998; Komarraju, Karau & Schmeck, 2009; Nofle & Robins, 2007). The other noncognitive predictor scale and motivation scale used in this study was Raven's Advanced Progressive Matrices (APM). The APM was developed to assess a component of an underlying common or general factor of intelligence, and is also identified as educative ability (Raven, 1993; Thompson & Rohde, 2007). Educative mental activity is where a person tries to make meaning out of confusion, developing new insights, and going beyond the given materials to perceive things that may not be immediately obvious. Many people are not prepared to do this, preferring to manipulate the pieces guided only by an impression of the whole or the sum of the parts. As such, the APM incorporates a values component and a conation component (effort, will, determination). This activity also involves forming constructs that assist in the handling of complex problem solving. The APM measures the ability to decompose problems into manageable sub-problems, manage their logical solving order, reassemble their various solutions, and the solution of the problem as a whole.

The third predictor domain, labeled as personal qualities (Camara , 2005), included a student's portfolio and essay scores collected after the student's freshmen or Core year in the College of Design. The forth predictor domain included information on the student's high school location, whether it was in-state or out-of-state from the

university under study, as well as information on alumni parents.

The success measure, or criterion variable, used in this study was a student's cumulative GPA. While the literature does caution on some of the problems of using GPA, the benefit is it is readily available for all students. Performance assessments of design projects or best-work portfolios obtained in a student's senior year may be a more accurate indicator of a student's design ability and success, but they tend to be very time-consuming to assess, and they have potential problems with inter-rater reliability and validity.

PROCEDURE

The personality and motivation scale data were collected from two online surveys, while the ACT and high school data were obtained from academic advisors and departmental representatives in the college. Email invitations were sent out to all undergraduate students in the four design disciplines with links to the online surveys. Follow-up reminder emails were issued and some online data collection was obtained from designated in-class time.

RESULTS

A DESCRIPTION OF THE SAMPLE

Of the 797 undergraduate students in the college of design, a total of 145 students completed both of the online survey questionnaires with a response rate of 18%. There were 8 architecture, 28 graphic design, 76 interior design, and 33 landscape architecture student respondents. The overall group consisted of 51 sophomores, 61 juniors, 18 seniors, and 15 Fifth Year students. The landscape architecture and architecture programs are five year programs, while interior design and graphic design are four year programs. Sixteen percent of the students had parents that were alumni, and 72% students graduated from high schools that were in-state.

¹ ACT English, Math, Reading, Science, Rhetoric, Elementary Algebra, Algebra-Geometry, Social Studies, and Algebra.

Figure 1. Survey respondents.

As stated previously, there were five main data categories in this study, which included 1) the Big Five Personality Test, 2) Raven's Progressive Matrices as a motivation scale, 3) ACT standardized test scores, 4) high school data, and 5) demographic data such as number of hours a student worked outside of school, alumni parents, and the location of the student's high school. Data from the portfolio and essay scores of the students' Core year is still being collected for all 797 students in the college of design, but will be a part of a future analysis.

THE FOUR DISCIPLINE ANALYSES

Multiple regression statistical analyses were conducted to examine the causal relationships between the variables for students in architecture, graphic design, interior design, and landscape architecture. The dependent variable used was the student's cumulative GPA, which defined a student's "success" in academics for this study. Two separate regression analyses were run; one with the ACT Composite score and the other with the ACT subscores. The rest of the independent variables included the five personality factors (conscientiousness, extroversion, neuroticism, openness, and agreeableness), high school GPA and rank, and the APM motivation score.

The best model included the Big Five Personality *conscientiousness* factor (BFIC), high school rank, and ACT English score². The best model using the ACT Composite score included BFIC, ACT Composite, and high school rank. When just the personality

² This model had an F ratio of 20.20 and an Adjusted R Squared value of .326.

factors were entered into the regression model with GPA as the dependent variable, openness and conscientiousness were significant. This result is consistent with previous research in predicting academic success with personality factors.

INTERIOR DESIGN ANALYSES

Like the four-discipline analyses, the interior design analysis regression models first started with the full set of variables. The full model with the APM, personality test, ACT subscores, and high school data produced the best model consisting of the Big Five Personality *agreeableness* factor (BFIA), high school rank, ACT English, and ACT Geometry-Trigonometry (negatively significant)³. Similarly, the model with the ACT composite score yielded the best model with BFIA, high school rank, and the ACT composite. However, the overall best model for interior design was the one without the personality factors included. In this model the significant factors were high school rank and ACT composite⁴.

GRAPHIC DESIGN ANALYSES

The graphic design regression models started with the full model with the APM, personality test, ACT subscores, and high school data. Unlike the two previous analyses, the best graphic design model produced several significant factors including: the Big Five Personality *neuroticism* factor (BFIN), the Big Five Personality *openness* factor (BFIO), high school GPA, high school rank, ACT English, ACT Reading, ACT Science, and ACT Algebra. Five of these factors were negatively significant, BFIN, BFIO, high school GPA, ACT Science, and ACT Algebra.⁵ When the regression model with ACT composite was used instead of the individual ACT subscores, the best model included the significant factors of APM, BFIC, high school GPA (negatively significant), and high school rank⁶.

³ This model had an F ratio of 8.47 and an Adjusted R Squared value of .396.

⁴ The F ratio for this model was 16.14 and an Adjusted R Squared value of .290.

⁵ The F ratio for this model was 11.68 with an Adjusted R Squared value of .781.

⁶ The F ratio for this model was 6.71 with an Adjusted R Squared value of .458.

	Overall	Graphic	Interior	Landscape	Architecture
With ACT Comp	BFIC, HS Rank, ACT_Comp	APM, BFIC, HS GPA (neg), HS Rank	BFIA, HS Rank, ACT_Comp	BFIC, BFIO, HS Rank	HS GPA, HS Rank, ACT_Comp
With ACT Subscores	BFIC, HS Rank, ACT_Engl	HS Rank, ACT_Engl, ACT_Read	BFIA, HS Rank, ACT_Engl, ACT_Geom-Trig (neg)	BFIC, BFIO, ACT_Science, ACT_ALG-GEOM (neg), ACT_Social Studies	ACT_Elementary Alg (neg), ACT_Geom-Trig, ACT_Social Studies, HS GPA

Figure 2. Prediction model summaries for overall group and individual design disciplines.

LANDSCAPE ARCHITECTURE

The same regression analyses were run for the landscape architecture cases as mentioned above. In the first regression model with the ACT composite score, personality test, APM, and high school data, the best model included three significant factors: BFIC, BFIO, and high school rank. All of these factors were positively significant⁷. The best model, using the ACT subscores with the rest of the independent variables produced a model with five significant factors: BFIC, BFIO, Act Science, Act Algebra-Geometry (negatively significant), and ACT Social Studies⁸.

ARCHITECTURE

There were not enough architecture participants to run the regression model with APM and the personality test, so the models were run using the ACT scores and the high school data. Using the ACT subscores, the best model included the following significant factors: high school GPA, ACT Elementary Algebra (negatively significant), ACT Geometry-Trigonometry, and ACT Social Studies⁹. In comparison, using the ACT composite score with the high school GPA and rank in the regression model yielded all of the three factors significant¹⁰.

DISCUSSION

The overall and individual design discipline analyses uncovered both similarities and differences across the regression models. First, when using the ACT

Composite score in the models, all four disciplines and the overall group included high school rank and ACT Composite scores as significant predictors of a student's cumulative GPA. The Big Five factor of conscientiousness was also significant in the overall group, graphic design, and landscape architecture students. Conscientiousness has been shown to predict GPA in previous prediction studies, and seems to make logical sense that these students, by definition, have a "disposition toward purposeful, determined, and goal-directed behavior."

When using the ACT subscores, there were some noticeable differences and similarities with the groups. In the overall group, ACT English was a significant factor. This was also significant in the graphic design, and interior design groups. The ACT math subscores showed negative significance in several groups. In interior design, the ACT Geometry-Trigonometry was negatively significant, while ACT Algebra was negative for the graphic design group, and ACT Algebra-Geometry was negative for the landscape architecture group.

In terms of the Big Five personality factors in the groups, conscientiousness and openness were significant in the overall group, while conscientiousness was shown to be significant in the graphic design and landscape architecture groups. Interestingly, agreeableness was significant only with the interior design students. Neuroticism and openness was negatively significant in the graphic design group, while openness was positively significant in the landscape architecture group. In previous personality research, openness was shown to indicate longevity in higher education.

The APM was a significant factor in only one group, the graphic design students. It was included in the

⁷ This yielded an F ratio of 12.37 and an Adjusted R Squared value of .516.

⁸ The F ratio was 21.01 and the Adjusted R Squared value was .781.

⁹ The F ratio for this model was 20.85 and the Adjusted R Squared value was .30.

¹⁰ The F ratio for this model was 35.78 and the Adjusted R Squared value was .25.

model with conscientiousness (BFIC), high school rank, and high school GPA (negative significance). More research is needed to better evaluate the APM as a predictor in academic success, especially since there were not enough architecture respondents to run valid models with that variable.

Traditional selection criteria have been composed of a student's high school data such as GPA and rank, as well as standardized test scores such as the ACT. However, motivation scales such as Raven's Advanced Progressive Matrices (APM) are not widely known or used in higher education selection processes. This is also true with tests on personality traits. An alternative use of such scales may be for formative assessment, where they can be administered to students already in design programs, so instructors may better assess the student more holistically.

SIGNIFICANCE

There are currently few prediction studies that focus on the art and design fields. Moreover, this study is the first study to comprehensively look at the design disciplines, noting both similarities and differences within the areas of architecture, graphic design, interior design, and landscape architecture. The results of this study begin to provide insight into the effectiveness of current admissions criteria and alternative prediction measures that have been proposed by some education scholars.

Deciding whether or not to admit a certain student into an enrollment managed program is a high-stakes decision. This decision can influence a student's future career and life direction. Not all students take tests well, and not all tests provide a well-rounded, accurate picture of the design potential and motivational tendencies of a student. Therefore, the admissions criteria and process in higher education demand diligent, current, and rigorous research that provides the basis of a program's admissions policies.

REFERENCES

- Barrick, M.R., & Mount, M.K. (1991). The Big Five personality dimensions and job performance: A meta-analysis. *Personnel Psychology*, 44, 1-26.
- Barrick, M.R., & Mount, M.K., & Gupta, R. (2003). Meta-analysis of the relationship between the five factor model of personality and Holland's occupational types. *Personnel Psychology*, 56, 45-74.
- Camara, W.J. (2005). Broadening predictors of college success. In W.J. Camara, E.W. Kimmel (Eds.), *Choosing students: Higher education admission tools for the 21st century* (pp. 81-105). Mahway, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Publishers.
- Conard, M.A. (2006). Aptitude is not enough: How personality and behavior predict academic performance. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 40, 339-346.
- Duckworth, A.L., & Seligman, M.E.P. (2005). Self-discipline outdoes IQ in predicting academic performance in adolescents. *Psychological Science*, 16, 939-944.
- Goldberg, L.R., & Kilkowski, J.M. (1985). The prediction of semantic consistency in self-descriptions: Characteristics of persons and of terms that affect the consistency of responses to synonym and antonym pairs. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 48, 82-98.
- Komarraju, M., Karau, S.J., & Schmeck, R.R. (2009). Role of the Big Five personality traits in predicting college students' academic motivation and achievement. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 19, 47-52.
- Larson, L.M., Rottinghaus, P.J., & Borgen, F.H. (2002). Meta-analyses of Big Six interests and Big Five personality factors. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 61, 217-239.
- Loehlin, J. C., McCrae, R. R., Costa, P. T., Jr., & John, O. P. (1998). Heritabilities of common and measure-specific components of the Big Five personality factors. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 32, 431-453.
- Noftle, E.E., & Robins, R.W. (2007). Personality predictors of Academic Outcomes: Big Five correlates of GPA and SAT scores. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 93, 116-130.
- Raven, J., Raven, J.C., & Court, J.H. (1993). *Manual for Raven's Progressive Matrices and Vocabulary Scales: General Overview*. 1993 ed., Oxford: Oxford Psychologists Press.
- Sedlacek, W.E. (2003). Alternative admissions and scholarship selection measures in higher education. *Measurement and Evaluation in Counseling and Development*, v 35, 263-272.
- Thompson, L.A., Rohde, T.E. (2007). *Predicting academic achievement with cognitive ability*. *Intelligence: a multidisciplinary journal*, vol 35, 1, pp. 83-92.
- Thoresen, C.J., Kaplan, S.A., Barsky, A.P., Warren, C.R., & de Chermont, K. (2003). The affective underpinnings of job perceptions and attitudes: A meta-analytic review and integration. *Psychological Bulletin*, 129, 914-945.